

From macro to micro: Comprehensive marine beach litter analysis using portable NIR[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The exponential growth of plastic production, combined with inadequate management of plastic waste, is increasing plastic pollution across all environments. Over the past decade, many countries have developed national strategies to monitor litter in marine environments, and on beaches these often involve monitoring either macrolitter and/or microlitter. Understanding the dynamics between different size fractions in the environment is crucial for a better understanding of the plastic cycle. Challenges remain in linking the information obtained from existing monitoring strategies: detailed categorisation of macrolitter based on the Joint List of Litter Categories developed by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive Technical Group on Marine Litter, and the analysis of microplastics from beach sediments, which usually includes determining morphological characteristics, colour, size, and chemical composition. The determination of polymer types in plastic macrolitter is not part of current monitoring. This study presents the first comprehensive analysis of marine beach litter in Slovenia, focusing on all three size classes of marine litter: macrolitter, mesolitter, and microlitter, and demonstrates the difficulties in comparing data between these size classes. The average densities observed were 0.38 macrolitter m⁻², 29.42 mesolitter m⁻² and 27.51 microlitter kg⁻¹ dry sediment. The majority of macrolitter originated from building and construction, as well as items related to food consumption. By introducing polymer type identification, the accuracy and efficiency of litter categorisation can be improved, contributing to a more precise understanding of the correlation between different size classes, litter composition, dynamics, and sources of plastic pollution in coastal areas.

1. Introduction

Global plastic production has increased from 1.5 million tons (Mt) in 1950 to more than 400 Mt. in 2022 (PlasticsEurope, 2023), which has led to a significant increase in generation of plastic waste. Much of this waste ends up in landfills or as litter, polluting terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Nayanathara Thathsarani Pilapitiya and Ratnayake, 2024). Between 1950 and 2015, 6300 million tons of plastic waste were generated, of which it is estimated that only 9 % was recycled and 60 % landfilled (Geyer et al., 2017). Studies highlight the ubiquity of plastic pollution, with plastics ranging from macro to micro sizes found in ecosystems from ocean trenches (Abel et al., 2023) to remote mountain ranges (Tsering et al., 2022). Despite more than a decade of monitoring efforts in the marine environment, the dynamics between different size

fractions of litter remain poorly understood (Windsor et al., 2019). Understanding the occurrence and impact of plastic pollution is crucial for the development of effective strategies to protect the environment (Wright et al., 2013).

The main legislation focusing on protecting the marine environment across Europe is the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008) adopted in 2008. The aim of the MSFD is to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) for all marine waters, including the Baltic Sea, the North-East Atlantic, the Mediterranean Sea, and the Black Sea. This requires the establishment of monitoring programmes in all European Member States, enabling regular assessment of the state of the marine environment based on 11 qualitative descriptors, with Descriptor 10 stating that “properties and quantities of marine litter do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment” (European Commission, 2017). The

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establishment of regular litter monitoring programmes contributes to the evidence base for various policy initiatives addressing plastic pollution, such as the Single Use Plastic Directive and the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (Nielsen et al., 2023). Regular monitoring programmes rely on harmonised protocols provided by the Technical Group on Marine Litter (TGML) in the document Guidance on Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas (Hanke et al., 2013), last updated in 2023 (Galgani et al., 2023) or developed in other projects (Gago et al., 2019). The guidance document covers methods for litter monitoring on the coastline, the seafloor, the sea surface, and interactions with biota (ingestion and entanglement), in different size categories – macrolitter (MaL, above 2.5 cm), mesolitter (MeL, between 5 mm and 2.5 cm), and microlitter (ML, between 1 µm and 5 mm) (Gajst et al., 2016; Vlachogianni and Scoullou, 2023). Even though the methodology for MeL monitoring is included in the TGML Guidelines document, it is not considered within the MSFD (Galgani et al., 2024).

The most common method for monitoring marine MaL is beach assessment (Haseler et al., 2025). According to the latest TGML guidelines (Galgani et al., 2023), collected beach litter is classified into 9 main categories based on material type (chemicals, clothing/textiles, food waste, glass/ceramics, metal, plastics/artificial polymers, paper/cardboard, rubber and processed/worked wood). This is the lowest level of detail in the hierarchy of the joint list of litter categories (Fleet et al., 2021). The second level comprises the use categories, including litter items related to agriculture, aquaculture, clothing, building and construction, food consumption, fisheries, personal hygiene and care, medicine, recreation, smoking, vehicles, hunting, and, the undefined use category. The fifth and highest level of detail represents the 183 categories that account for different size classes of individual litter items.

According to Galgani et al. (2023), the classification of MaL items found during beach litter monitoring does not require identification of polymer types within the plastics/artificial polymers category. Detailed identification of polymer types would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the types and sources of litter affecting the coastal environment, enabling policymakers to gain a clearer overview and better understanding of the pollution present, so they can take more effective action and implement more successful restriction policies. Additionally, correlations of different litter size classes could be made based on polymer types.

Near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is a promising method for identifying plastics in environmental samples (Zou et al., 2025), providing a rapid and non-destructive analytical approach.

The present study aims to assess the abundance and composition of MaL, MeL and ML on a selected beach in Slovenia. The objective of the study was to collect baseline seasonal data the abundance and composition of all three beach litter size classes and their possible correlations, representing the first comprehensive study of its kind in Slovenia. Additionally, the study assesses the effectiveness of NIR spectroscopy for beach litter monitoring campaigns by confirming the NIR analysis results of plastic MaL and MeL collected with Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. It highlights both the strengths and limitations of portable NIR technology for analysing plastics in the environment and offer insights into potential improvements for future applications. Furthermore it analyses the use categories of MaL as defined by Fleet et al. (2021) to assess the sources of MaL.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The Slovenian Coast is located at the far northern end of the Mediterranean, along the Gulf of Trieste in the northernmost part of the Adriatic Sea. Compared with the rest of the Adriatic, the surface sea currents in the northern Adriatic, including the Slovenian section, are substantially weaker. Due to the shallowness of the Gulf of Trieste, the direction and speed of the currents are closely linked to the prevailing

weather conditions. Their speed and direction are influenced by strong winds, and the entire water column is affected by the tide. The greatest difference between high and low tide exceeds 180 cm. The main sea current flows from Istria northwards and returns along the Italian coast (Grubar, 2010).

In addition to Koper, Izola and Piran, Ankaran is one of the four Slovenian coastal municipalities with over 90,000 inhabitants (Čok, 2024). The selected sampling unit was a beach located in Ankaran (Slovenia) in the Bay of San Bartolomeo (Fig. 1) in the southwest of the country. According to Čok (2024), there are three official and six other bathing sites in the municipality of Ankaran. The substrate consists of approximately (estimated by the authors) 90 % sand, with some individual pebbles and rocks. The greater surrounding area comprises a mix of coastal, infrastructural, natural and semi-natural areas, including the protected natural coastline and the Debeli Rtič Landscape Park. Nearly half of the municipality of Ankaran's territory consists of building land (48.5 %; including residential areas, industrial zones, tourism and recreation areas, and traffic zones), followed by agricultural land (34.8 %), forests (14.2 %), water bodies (1.4 %) and other uses (1.2 %) (Jug et al., 2020). The predominance of fine sand allows for the monitoring of MaL, as well as MeL and ML. This beach was chosen as the study area because there are no other predominantly sandy beaches in Slovenia that enable monitoring of all three litter sizes. The entire beach is 70 m long and there is a mussel farm nearby (Fig. 1).

The beach is accessible throughout the year, has a concave shape and is situated in a semi-urban environment. A line of vegetation behind which lies a road, defines the back of the beach, which is also the top line of the supratidal zone.

2.2. Sampling and sample analysis

MaL, MeL and ML were collected seasonally during four surveys in 2024: February (winter), April (spring), July (summer) and October (autumn). The width of the beach was measured during each survey as it changes with the tide. As suggested in the TGML Guidelines (Galgani et al., 2023), ML samples were taken first, followed by MeL and then MaL, to avoid disturbing the distribution of ML and MeL in the study area.

2.2.1. Microlitter (ML)

ML sampling and analysis were conducted by the Institute for Water of the Republic of Slovenia (IWRS), which is performing the national litter monitoring programme in Slovenia (Kovač Viršek et al., 2024) that is under the jurisdiction of Slovenian Environment Agency since 2022 (Republika Slovenija, 2022). Except for the winter sample, sampling was conducted at the same location and time. ML samples were collected across the entire sampling point, distributed along transects parallel to the coastline in both the intertidal and supratidal zones. During each microlitter sampling event (once per season), nine samples were taken by sampling a 10 × 10 cm area of the upper 3–5 cm layer of sediment using a metal trowel. The samples were stored in glass jars that had been washed before sampling and rinsed with ultrapure water.

In the laboratory, the sediment sample was transferred to two glass Petri dishes (90 mm diameter, rinsed with ultrapure water) so that both Petri dishes were filled, but not the entire sample from the glass jar was analysed, assuming the sample was homogeneous. The sediment in the Petri dishes was then dried in an oven (Thermo Scientific Heratherm Advanced Protocol Oven, Heratherm OGS60) at 40 °C until constant weight was achieved. The dried sediment (on average 140 g per sample) was then transferred to saturated NaCl solution, covered with aluminium foil, and thoroughly mixed. The mixture was left to settle for approximately seven hours, after which the supernatant was removed to a separate beaker. The density separation was repeated twice with saturated NaCl solution, mixed thoroughly, and left to settle for 16 h, after which the supernatant was removed. The entire supernatant from the density separation was filtered through a nylon filter (80 µm pore

Fig. 1. Study area; Beach located in the Bay of San Bartolomeo, Ankaran (Slovenia). Map prepared by R. Soczka Mandac, IWRS; based on data available from Surveying and mapping authority of the Republic of Slovenia (SMA), Slovenian Water Agency (DRSV), Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Nature Conservation (IRSNC).

size; Merck, Cork, Ireland) using vacuum filtration, and the beaker was rinsed three times with ultrapure water. The filter was placed in a clean, labelled glass Petri dish and analysed for the presence of ML particles under a stereomicroscope (Stereo Discovery V8, Zeiss, Jena, Germany; with AxioVision Zen 3.6 blue edition software for image analysis). Each particle was photographed, categorised, measured, and then analysed with a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR; RaptIR microscope coupled with Nicolet iS50 spectrometer; Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA; Omnic Paradigm v. 2.4 software) or a Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA; Spectrum IR v.10.6.2.1159 software). With the Nicolet iS50, spectra were collected over a spectral range of 4000–650 cm^{-1} , 16 scans per sample or background, and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in reflectance mode. The analysis was performed at room temperature.

With the Spectrum Two spectrometer, spectra were collected using attenuated total reflection (ATR) over a spectral range of 4000–450 cm^{-1} , 4 scans per sample or background, and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Plastic ML items were placed on the surface of the ATR crystal to record the spectra. The outer surface of the ATR crystal was cleaned with 70 % ethanol after each recording. The recorded spectra were compared with a reference spectral library, and a match of more than 75 % was accepted. A match of less than 75 % was confirmed manually, or the spectral acquisition of the sample was repeated (usually with a higher scan setting) until an acceptable result was obtained. For some particles a lower reference library % match was accepted based on expert judgment. Results were expressed as number of ML particles per kg of dry sediment. Based on the results of chemical analysis, ML was categorised in subcategories (modified Table 3.3 in Galgani et al., 2023; Supplementary material, Table 1). According to the nine main categories (Fleet et al., 2021) used for MaL and MeL classification, the ML was also classified accordingly, based on the results of the chemical analysis of

Table 1

Measurements of beach width at the time of sampling in different seasons.

Season	Beach width [m]	Beach area when collecting litter [m ²]
Winter	23 / 34.8*	1610 / 2436*
Spring	24.5	1715
Summer	28	1960
Autumn	25	1750

* The beach width and calculated area when IWRS conducted the ML sampling.

the extracted particles.

2.2.2. Mesolitter (MeL)

MeL sediment samples were taken in two transects across the beach prior to the collection of MaL. The width and length of the transects were recorded during each survey, as they were adjusted according to the conditions (such as the distribution of larger rocks in the sampling unit). The top 1–2 cm of the entire transect was transferred with a metal trowel to a metal sieve with a mesh size of 5 mm. The sample was stored in a plastic bag and analysed in the laboratory.

All identified MeL items were sorted, counted, and categorised (e.g. plastic, metal, glass, etc.), and plastic items were further analysed for polymer type with a portable near-infrared spectrometer (NIR; Matoha Plastell, London, UK). Calibration of the instrument prior to sample measurements was performed automatically at start-up. However, recalibration was conducted every 30 min, and the scanning area was cleaned with 70 % ethanol. Each litter item was placed on the glass surface above the IR light source and detector to measure reflectance at wavelengths of 1550–1950 nm. If the item was heavily soiled, it was washed with ethanol and wiped to expose the plastic surface for

analysis. The spectra obtained were compared with the reference library provided by Matoha, which included the following materials: Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), Polyethylene (PE), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), Polypropylene (PP), Polystyrene (PS), Polycarbonate (PC), Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS), Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA), Polyamide (PA), Polylactic Acid (PLA), Polyurethane (PU), Polyether Ether Ketone (PEEK), Polyoxymethylene (POM), Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG), Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU), Silicone (SIL), Rubber (RUB), and Paper. All hits with a medium or high confidence level were accepted. The accuracy of the results obtained with the NIR spectrometer was evaluated with FTIR.

FTIR spectra were acquired using a Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer with a Universal ATR with diamond crystal (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). Data were collected over a spectral range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} (12 scans per sample or background) at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in reflectance mode. The spectrum of the crystal surface was recorded and used as background; the analysis was performed at room temperature. Plastic litter items were placed on the surface of the ATR crystal to record the spectra. The outer surface of the ATR crystal was cleaned with 70 % ethanol after each recording. The recorded spectra were compared with a reference spectral library, and a match of more than 75 % was accepted. A match of less than 75 % was confirmed manually, or the spectral acquisition of the sample was repeated until an acceptable result was obtained. The results were expressed as the number of litter items per 100 m^2 to assess possible correlations with MaL. Based on the results of chemical analysis, MeL was categorised in the same subcategories as ML.

2.2.3. Macrolitter (MaL)

MaL was systematically collected in plastic bags along the entire beach by following a path, transverse to the water edge and collecting all MaL bigger than 2.5 cm. The items were then sorted, counted, weighed and categorised according to Joint list of litter categories (Fleet et al., 2021). Additionally, plastic litter items were characterized by polymer type using the same methodology as MeL items. The number of MaL items was extrapolated to a 100 m long beach and expressed as number of items per m^2 of beach. Based on the results of chemical analysis, MaL was categorised in the same subcategories as MeL and ML. Additionally, all MaL was classified into use categories defined by the Joint list of litter categories (Fleet et al., 2021).

2.3. Data analysis

The density of the beach litter (macro and meso) was calculated as.

$$D = \frac{n}{w \times l} \quad (1)$$

where D is the density of litter items per m^2 ; n is the number of litter items collected; w and l are the width and length of the sampling unit, respectively. The number of items per 100 m of beach length was also calculated.

The cleanliness of the beaches was assessed using the Clean Coast Index (CCI) (Alkalay et al., 2007): $CCI = D \times k$ (2), where D is the density of MaL per m^2 and k is a constant of 20. According to the CCI scale, values from 0 to 2 indicate very clean beaches, 2–5 clean, 5–10 moderately clean, 10–20 dirty and > 20 extremely dirty. To ensure data comparability, all MaL, MeL and ML items analysed for polymer type were classified into different subcategories based on the chemical analysis. Additionally, ML particles were classified into the same nine main categories as MeL and MaL and a correlation comparison was made. Statistical analysis was conducted with Past v. 4.16c (Hammer et al., 2001) using the Pearson correlation analysis for correlation among different litter size classes and the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity analysis to evaluate the similarity of the ML, MeL, and MaL in terms of their polymer composition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Litter abundance

In 2024, a total of four beach surveys were conducted, one in each season. A total of 2636 MaL, 831 MeL items were classified, recorded, and removed from a cumulative area of 7035 m^2 (the combined area of the four surveys, depending on the width of the beach (Table 1) at the time of sampling). Altogether there were 140 ML particles extracted from 5.14 kg of dry beach sediment.

Table 2 presents the average and median number of litter items per 100 m beach and per m^2 . According to the calculated CCI based on the average macro data, the beach at Lazaret (Ankaran) is moderately clean. However, the average litter density per 100 m beach (941 ± 98) is well above the European threshold value of 20 litter items per 100 m (Van Loon et al., 2020) and the threshold value of 130 litter items/100 m (UNEP/MAP, 2021). It should be noted that reporting litter density only per 100 m of beach, as required by the European MSFD, could lead to over- or underestimation of litter items depending on the width of the beach and hinders accurate comparisons between locations where sampling unit widths differ significantly. For example, if the average number of MaL items per 100 m of beach is 1000, there is a significant difference if these 1000 items are found on a beach that is 5 m wide (0.2 items m^{-2}) compared to a beach that is 50 m wide (2 items m^{-2}). Therefore, we recommend always specifying the number of MaL items per surveyed area as well, which is especially important for comparison with MeL and ML results.

Considering the average number of items per m^2 , there were 77 times more MeL items per m^2 than MaL. The abundance of MaL is even higher than a study conducted in the Adriatic-Ionian macroregion by Vlachogianni et al. (2018), where one of the highest average number of MaL was found in Strunjan, Slovenia (828 MaL/100 m) whereas the two beaches in the Northern Italy were cleaner, with 375 and 192 MaL per 100 m., which could be due to the fact that the selected study site is concave shape, which retain more litter (Brennan et al., 2018). The EU Coastline MaL trend report published in 2025 (MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter et al., 2025) states that in the Mediterranean a trend of 38 % reduction was seen from years 2015–2016 to 2020–2021, even though a study from a North-East Atlantic showed that at least six years of monitoring with 4 surveys per year is required to detect a 10 % reduction of MaL (Schulz et al., 2019).

The results of ML sediment analysis (Table 3) are given only in items per kg dry sediment. Due to the limitations of the methodology used, the results are not comparable with the macrolitter and MeL abundance. If the entire sediment sample taken from the 10×10 cm area were analysed, the results could also be given per m^2 , however with a high uncertainty since not only the surface layer of sediment was sampled. Difficulties in comparing the litter abundance with other studies were also evident where the sampling methods are not (at least) in accordance with the TGML Guidelines and not in accordance with the monitoring requirements within the MSFD (Haseler et al., 2019). For example, a study where sampling is conducted on 1 m^2 quadrants throughout a beach, collecting all litter items with a lower size limit of 1 mm (Markić et al., 2024), is difficult to compare with the present study, since the results are given as an average of all items bigger than 1 mm m^{-2} . The

Table 2

The average abundances of MaL and MeL are provided with the standard deviation, and the medians are provided with the median absolute deviation.

	Average n (100 m) ⁻¹ beach h \pm SD	Median n (100 m) ⁻¹ beach \pm MAD	Average n $\text{m}^{-2} \pm$ SD	Median n $\text{m}^{-2} \pm$ MAD	CCI
MaL	941 \pm 98	961 \pm 75	0.38 \pm 0.04	0.38 \pm 0.03	7.5
MeL	15,509 \pm 4315	16,600 \pm 3055	29.42 \pm 9.53	25.82 \pm 6.89	

Table 3

The average beach ML density in average number of items per kg dry sediment (average ± standard deviation, SD). The median beach ML density was calculated per kg dry sediment (median ± median absolute deviation, MAD).

	Average n kg ⁻¹ dry sediment ± SD	Median n kg ⁻¹ dry sediment ± MAD
ML	27.51 ± 6.44	28.54 ± 4.58

highest abundance of ML was in winter (30.10 ML kg⁻¹ dry sediment) and spring (34.08 ML kg⁻¹ dry sediment), which is comparable to other studies (Jaouani et al., 2022). The lowest amount was in autumn (18.89 ML kg⁻¹ dry sediment) and in summer there were 26.97 ML kg⁻¹ dry sediment.

3.2. Litter composition

The top 10 MaL subcategories according to the Joint list of litter categories per season are shown in Fig. 2. In winter, all top 10 MaL categories belong to plastics. The most frequently found items were non-foamed plastic fragments between 2.5 and 50 cm in their longest dimension (J79), accounting for 22.7 % of the total litter collected in winter, followed by hard plastic cups and lids (J227) at 16.0 %, other glass items (J210) at 15.1 %, and glass or ceramic construction materials (J204) at 6.5 %.

In spring, the J79 category was in second place (10.3 %), while the most common category was glass and ceramic fragments between 2.5 and 50 cm in size (34.2 %). As in winter, hard plastic cups and lids

Fig. 2. The top 10 MaL categories per season, calculated as a percentage based on the total number of items found.

accounted for 9.8 % of the total litter found, followed by glass and ceramic construction materials (8.4 %) and plastic crisp packets and sweet wrappers (J30).

The glass/ceramics category was most strongly represented in the summer and autumn surveys (Fig. 3). In both cases, glass/ceramic construction materials (J204) and glass/ceramic fragments (J208) took first and second place. They accounted for 49.3 % of the total litter found in summer and 68.1 % in autumn. In both seasons, fragments of non-foamed plastic (J79) was in third place, and the remaining categories accounted for less than 7 % of the total items found.

The collected MaL, MeL and ML was classified into nine main categories according to the Joint list (Fleet et al., 2021). An additional category (Other) was added to ML for particles where the ML items, based on the chemical analysis, did not clearly fit into any of the existing main categories.

In order to compare and test for correlation between all different litter size classes, the subcategories of polymer types (Supplementary material, Table 1) and the nine main categories according to the Joint list of litter categories were compared. Pearson correlation analysis based on the material composition of ML, MeL, and MaL showed results similar to those for polymer composition. Stronger and statistically significant correlations were observed between macro and meso samples. The analysis also revealed more statistically significant and stronger correlations between micro samples collected in winter or spring and those collected in spring and autumn (Supplementary material, Fig. 1).

Fig. 4 shows the seasonal abundance of plastic ML and MeL by type. Due to the small sample size and the lack of a common denominator (ML is reported per kg dry sediment and MeL per m²), no statistical analysis

was conducted. The results indicate that the highest amount of ML occurred in spring, with abundance decreasing until autumn. Winter was comparable to spring. No clear trend can be observed in plastic MeL items; however, winter and summer, as well as spring and autumn, appear more similar in terms of abundance.

3.3. Polymer types of plastic MaL, MeL and ML

3.3.1. Plastic macrolitter

Detailed results of MaL categories within each polymer type per season can be found in Table 2 of the Supplementary material. The most common MaL category for PS was cups and lids (J227), plastic cutlery (J228) and non-foamed plastic fragments (J79). Most PVC items belonged to the category of fragments made of non-foamed plastic (J79). In all 4 seasons, the most common PP litter belonged to mussel's mesh bags (J45) and fragments of non-foamed plastic (J79). PE was more common in summer and autumn in the form of fragments of non-foamed plastic (J79), plastic sheets (J67) and plastic caps (J23, J21). The majority of PET was collected in spring and autumn, mainly as fragments of non-foamed plastic (J79), bottles (J7) and strings (J242). Similarly, PA was also found mainly in spring and autumn in the form of cable ties (J93) and fishing line (J59).

Overall, NIR analysis proved to be accurate for 95.1 % of the plastic MaL items analysed. The most common misidentifications of NIR compared to FTIR results (Supplementary material, Table 6) were two items identified as ABS, where FTIR analysis revealed that they were in fact PS. This could be improved by adding more spectra to the NIR spectrometer reference library. Several items that were black or dirty (with no clean, exposed plastic surface) NIR spectrometer identified as

Fig. 3. Representation of different categories in different size classes through the four seasons as well as the yearly sum.

Fig. 4. Seasonal abundance of plastic ML (a) and MeL (b) by type.

PU (FTIR identified them as PET and PP). Other incorrect identifications (PMMA, PA, PS and PVC) are due to the absence of the materials in the NIRs' reference library (PDP, PVDF, CP, various adhesives).

3.3.2. Plastic mesolitter

Plastic MeL was further classified into fragments, foils, fibres, or other categories. Polymer types within each category were then determined using a portable NIR spectrometer and confirmed by FTIR analysis. If the polymer type was misidentified by NIR, the chemical composition information was corrected accordingly, and the misidentification was recorded for calculation of the correctly identified items. Overall, the NIR analysis was accurate for 96.2 % of all plastic mesolitter items analysed. Two items were misidentified by NIR as PE or PP (a fiber and a foil); FTIR analysis identified them as PE/PP (or PP/PE) copolymers. This could be improved by including copolymers in the reference library of the NIR spectrometer.

Three MeL categories were represented in all seasons, while the *other* category was present only in the autumn (Supplementary material, Fig. 4). Among the fragments, PS was the most abundant polymer in all seasons except in summer, when the majority of fragments were PE. The foils were mostly PVC in all seasons except in summer, when most were PE.

3.3.3. Plastic microlitter

Predominant type of ML in winter, spring and autumn were fragments (Fig. 5). In summer season, the amount of fragments and fibres was the same.

FTIR analysis results of Plastic ML particles are shown in Fig. 6. The highest variety of polymer types of plastic ML were observed in spring and summer. The majority of fragments in spring time were PE, in summer PET, followed by PE and OP (other plastics – group of less common plastic types; see Supplementary material, Table 1).

3.3.4. Correlation between plastic MaL, MeL and ML

Our research hypothesis was that the composition of all three litter size classes sampled simultaneously at the same location is interrelated, due to the fragmentation of larger litter items into smaller ones (from macro to meso and finally to micro sizes). compares the composition of plastic litter among the macro, meso, and micro size classes according to the main polymer group. It shows that the composition of MeL and MaL appears correlated, both in the types of polymers and their relative proportions among all identified polymers. A similar composition of ML to MeL and MaL is observed only in summer samples. To support these observations, we performed Pearson correlation analysis to estimate the statistical significance of the similarity of collected plastic MaL, MeL, and ML based on major polymer groups and additionally to compare the main categories by material of all litter items (Fleet et al., 2021).

Pearson correlation analysis (Fig. 8) supports the observation that there is a stronger, and in most cases statistically significant ($p < 0.05$; see also Supplementary material, Tables 3–6 and Fig. 1), positive correlation between the polymer composition of MaL and MeL sampled on the same day (season). There is also a statistically significant positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) between MaL collected across seasons and between MeL collected in autumn, winter, and spring. The correlation of

Fig. 5. Plastic ML percentages by type (fiber (FI), fragment (FR)) in different seasons.

Fig. 6. Plastic ML abundance per type of item (fiber (FI) or fragment (FR)) by polymer type in different seasons.

ML was statistically significant only between samples collected in spring and summer, or autumn and summer. Additionally, we observed a statistically significant correlation only between the ML collected in spring and the MeL collected in summer. All statistically significant and stronger correlations were positive.

To evaluate the similarity of the ML, MeL, and MaL in terms of their polymer composition, we used the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity analysis (Fig. 9). Clustering supported the observations from the Pearson correlation analysis, showing that, apart from the *meso* summer sample, MaL and MeL were more similar in polymer composition than ML. To enable better comparison and potential correlation between polymer groups, Primpke et al. (2018) suggest using their novel reference database that improves polymer identification and allows data comparison with other studies.

3.4. Sources of beach MaL

Fig. 10 shows the use categories of MaL from samples collected in four seasons. Differences are particularly evident between winter and spring compared to summer and autumn. The undefined use category accounted for the largest proportion in all four seasons, with 52.1 % and 53.2 % of all MaL items in summer and autumn, compared to 62.0 % and 66.8 % in winter and spring. The second and third most abundant use categories were building and construction related, and food consumption related. The proportion of the food consumption related category in winter (24.1 %) and spring (18.7 %) was about two to five times higher than in summer (8.3 %) and autumn (4.9 %). The proportion of the building and construction related category was about three to five times lower in winter (7.0 %) and spring (9.1 %) compared to summer (30.6 %) and autumn (37.9 %). Another difference between winter and spring compared to summer and autumn is the proportion of the fisheries related category, which was the fourth most abundant in winter (3.1 %) and spring (2.1 %) but among the less abundant categories in summer (0.6 %) and autumn (0.4 %). In contrast, the aquaculture related category had higher proportions in summer (2.2 %) and autumn (1.4 %) compared to winter (0.5 %) and spring (0.3 %). This may be due to more intensive harvesting of mussels during summer, driven by higher demand in restaurants (Ramšak et al., 2024) and due to the proximity of the beach to the mussel farm.

The smoking related category had a higher proportion of MaL only in summer (3.0 %), which may be linked to increased tourism during the summer months; for example, the number of overnight stays in all four

municipalities along the Slovenian coast exceeded 600,000 in July and August 2024, but was less than 100,000 in January and February (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2025). Interestingly, despite the fact that over 30 % Ankarán's municipality is agricultural land use, no considerable amount of agriculture related MaL were found.

It is difficult to confirm correlations between beach litter abundance and certain land uses (e.g. tourism and recreation) (Hengstmann et al., 2018), as litter abundance and composition depend on complex interactions between factors such as (but not limited to) beach use, wastewater and river discharges, beach location, climate conditions (e.g. wind), and hydrodynamics (Graca et al., 2017), although some studies state that the beach shape, substrate type and proximity to different sources affects the deposition of litter (Brennan et al., 2018; Hardesty et al., 2017; Hernandez et al., 2025). Wind data were gathered from a nearby oceanographic buoy Vida located in the middle of the Gulf of Trieste (45° 32.925' N, 13° 33.042' E) and operated by the Marine Biology Station in Piran, Slovenia (NIB, MBP, 2025). The data include average half-hour wind speeds and direction, analysed according to the eight main wind directions (N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW) for the week prior to sampling. Wind conditions during the seven days before each sampling were quite different (Supplementary material, Figs. 4–7). Before the winter sampling, winds were mostly from the south (25.0 % of the time) and southeast (28.1 % of the time), with stronger winds (above 2.5 m s⁻¹) blowing from the southeast. Before the spring sampling, winds were predominantly from the south (23.0 % of the time) and southeast (21.8 % of the time), with speeds between 1.5 and 2.5 m s⁻¹. Before the summer sampling, winds were mainly from the northeast (51.8 % of the time; known as bora in the Adriatic; (Cosoli et al., 2013)). While gusts of bora wind in the Northern Adriatic often exceed 30 m s⁻¹ (Bervida et al., 2019), wind speeds before the summer sampling were lower, mostly reaching between 0.5 and 1.5 m s⁻¹. Before the autumn sampling, winds were mainly from the south (32.1 % of the time).

3.5. Challenges

According to the TGML Guidelines (Galgani et al., 2023), when sampling all three size classes of litter, the recommended order is ML, MeL, and MaL to avoid disturbing the distribution of ML and MeL in the study area. The guidelines assume that most MeL is plastic and therefore suggest monitoring only the plastic fraction, with particular emphasis on plastic pellets. However, this study also included other MeL materials – glass/ceramics, metal, cloth/textiles, and food waste to enable data comparison with MaL. According to the guidelines, ML sampling and

Fig. 7. Proportion of different polymer groups in plastic ML, MeL and MaL in four seasons.

Fig. 8. Results of Pearson correlation analysis - correlation of plastic ML, MeL and MaL based on their polymer composition (showing r values, with values in boxes indicating statistically significant correlation p < 0.05). W = winter, SP = spring, SU = Summer, A = Autumn.

analysis should also focus on the plastic fraction, making it difficult to compare results across the three size classes. Additionally, when sampling all three litter size fractions at the same location, the TGML guidelines do not specify whether MeL items that are otherwise counted as MaL (e.g. cigarette butts; Table 3.3 in Galgani et al. (2023)), should be classified as MeL or MaL. Regarding results reporting, the guidelines are consistent with the units of measurement for the MSFD Descriptor 10 criteria, as specified in Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848. However, further harmonisation is needed in the requirements for reporting results, as the current approach suggested by the TGML Guidelines does not allow for comparison between size classes as seen in this study. For example, the requirement for MaL reporting is the number of MaL items per 100 m of beach, whereas ML should be reported in kg per dry sediment. We suggest to report all the results also as number of items per

area, since beach widths can vary, especially between different locations, but also within the same sampling unit due to tidal differences where the beach slope is low or level, as is the case in our sampling unit.

Theoretically, comparing all size classes by reporting results per area would resolve the issue. However, ML samples are typically collected from the top 3–5 cm of sediment. Ideally, the ML size range should correspond primarily to the top ~5 mm of the sediment surface, taking into account the maximum size of ML particle. However, no innovative techniques enabling accurate sampling of only this thin surface layer (~5 mm) are yet available. Sampling deeper layers (3–5 cm), as recommended in the guidelines, risks including larger items (MeL or MaL) that are not actually present on the sediment surface but are embedded below it and therefore should not be classified as surface MeL or MaL (only macro items at least partially visible from the surface should be

Fig. 9. Clustering based on polymer composition of micro, meso and macro samples (based on unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity analysis). W = winter, SP = spring, SU = Summer, A = Autumn.

sampled). Interestingly the majority of the studies investigating ML in sediments samples 2–6 cm top layer (Jualaong et al., 2021; Khuyen et al., 2021; Schröder et al., 2021) and rarely the “surface” is treated as the top 5 mm (Constant et al., 2023), followed by reporting of ML m^{-2} in addition to number of ML kg^{-1} dry sediment (Jualaong et al., 2021). Similarly, MeL sampling often targets the upper 1–2 cm, but this does not fully align with the theoretical size-based definitions. To harmonise sampling across size categories and improve comparability, we propose restricting sediment sampling depth to approximately the top 5 mm for all size classes and thereby limiting only to the actual surface layer of the sediment. This would allow all MeL (>5 mm) and MaL (>25 mm) items to be collected directly from the visible sediment surface, where they are more reliably detected, while also enabling quantification of ML per area. Reporting results in m^{-2} would also reduce the need for extrapolations from small subsamples, particularly for ML. Additionally, discrepancies in the spatial definition of sampling units (e.g., MaL sampling extending to the back of the beach, which may lie above the supratidal line) can influence interpretation regarding the origin and transport of

litter. At the present study site, this issue is minimised, as the back of the beach corresponds to the supratidal vegetation line, ensuring that the sampled area is consistently influenced by marine deposition processes.

Since 2008, when the Marine Strategy Framework Directive was introduced and member states began implementing monitoring programmes for marine litter in the environment, the sampling and analysis methods have still not been harmonised and do not allow for data comparison between locations. Additionally, different strategies have been adopted regarding the determination of litter size classes that are regularly monitored. In Slovenia, for example, six different beaches are monitored seasonally for MaL, another three beaches (not the same locations) for ML and MeL is not included in monitoring (Kovač Viršek et al., 2024). It is difficult to assess the efficiency of adopted regulations; for example, the success of the Single Use Plastic Directive (European Union, 2019) is difficult to measure based solely on data derived from ML monitoring, whereas regular monitoring of different size classes could allow possible correlations to be made based on litter occurrence, distribution and composition between different size classes. Due to the

Fig. 10. Percentages of MaL items in different use category as defined by Fleet et al., 2021 per season.

time required for synthetic materials to degrade and fragment, it can be assumed that differences in MeL and ML composition after effective measures are implemented would become apparent with a delay compared to the MaL fraction.

Current TGML guidelines (Galgani et al., 2023) propose a well-established MaL monitoring strategy and enable a more comprehensive analysis based on 183 categories (Fleet et al., 2021); however, they do not account for differences in reporting the abundance of litter in different size classes in different units (MaL in number of items per 100 m beach, ML in kg per dry sediment). Consequently, no correlation analysis can be made or conclusions drawn that would inform policy decisions or enable assessment of the effectiveness of adopted measures.

4. Conclusion

This study aimed to assess the abundance and composition of macrolitter (MaL), mesolitter (MeL) and microlitter (ML) on a selected beach in Ankaran, Slovenia. Baseline seasonal data were collected on the abundance and composition of all three beach litter size classes and their possible correlations. The average densities were 0.38 MaL m⁻², 29.42 MeL m⁻² and 27.51 ML kg⁻¹ dry sediment. A positive correlation was observed between the polymer composition of MaL and MeL per season, as well as between MaL samples collected across seasons and between MeL samples collected in autumn, winter, and spring. The correlation of micro samples was statistically significant only between samples collected in spring and summer, or autumn and summer. Further

analysis showed that, except for the meso summer sample, macro and meso samples were more similar in polymer composition than micro samples. The results indicate that further harmonisation in beach litter sampling and analysis is needed, particularly by addressing the difficulties in comparing data between macro, meso, and micro size classes. Additional data on litter abundance and occurrence from our pilot study, as well as improvements in sampling and sample analysis methods, are needed to gain sufficient understanding of litter composition and the factors affecting it.

Additionally, the study assessed the effectiveness of NIR spectroscopy for beach litter monitoring campaigns. It was demonstrated that introducing polymer identification using NIR spectroscopy to MaL and MeL, enables a (limited) comparison of polymer type proportions among various litter sizes across different seasons. The method proved efficient and reliable for more than 95 % of the plastic MaL and MeL analysed, which is consistent with other similar studies (Pakhomova et al., 2020). Integration of NIR, as a fast and reliable method for identifying polymer types, can facilitate plastic separation, improving the potential reuse of plastic litter found in various environments within plastics production chains, and can reduce the strain on landfills. The NIR spectrometer's reference library can be extended to include more polymer types to improve the performance of NIR analysis. Utilisation of NIR spectrometry is a fast, relatively affordable (compared to FTIR) and reliable tool that can provide additional information about polymer types complementing the Joint list of litter categories (Fleet et al., 2021), and contributing to better waste management strategies such as but not

limited to sorting and recycling processes. Based on this study, we recommend the integration of a portable NIR spectrometer into litter monitoring protocols.

Furthermore, the study analysed the use categories of MaL as defined by Fleet et al. (2021) to assess the sources of MaL. The main differences were observed between winter–spring and summer–autumn, demonstrating how changes in activities such as food consumption, construction, fisheries, and aquaculture influence the seasonal composition of MaL. These patterns highlight the need to consider seasonal variability when assessing MaL sources and designing targeted management measures. In addition to the unidentified use that was predominant in all seasons, most MaL originated from building and construction, as well as items related to food consumption. One identified source of litter in the summer was aquaculture, presumably due to increased activity and mussel farming near the selected beach during that period.

Analysis of wind speed and direction in the week prior to sampling beach litter was conducted as well. Although wind conditions clearly differed before each sampling, it remains unclear to what extent they affect the quantity and quality of the analysed litter, especially in relation to other factors such as varying human activities and pressures between seasons, different tide levels, and so on. Further research is required to determine which specific combination of factors (activities, winds, tides, etc.), and the relevant time frame before sampling, has the greatest influence on the analysed MaL, MeL, and ML data.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bizjak Tamara: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Bizjak Tine:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stres Blaž:** Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Likožar Blaž:** Funding acquisition. **Novak Uroš:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2025.119172>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abel, S.M., Wu, F., Primpke, S., Gerdt, G., Brandt, A., 2023. Journey to the deep: plastic pollution in the hadal of deep-sea trenches. *Environ. Pollut.* 333, 122078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.122078>.
- Alkalay, R., Pasternak, G., Zask, A., 2007. Clean-coast index—a new approach for beach cleanliness assessment. *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 50, 352–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2006.10.002>.
- Bervida, M., Stanič, S., Bergant, K., Strajnar, B., 2019. Near-ground profile of bora wind speed at Razdrto, Slovenia. *Atmosphere* 10, 601. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos10100601>.
- Brennan, E., Wilcox, C., Hardesty, B.D., 2018. Connecting flux, deposition and resuspension in coastal debris surveys. *Sci. Total Environ.* 644, 1019–1026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.352>.
- Čok, G., 2024. Formal and informal natural bathing sites and beaches in the Slovenian coastal zone: challenges in the field of spatial inventory and planning. *ANNALES, SERIES HISTORIA ET SOCIOLOGIA* 34, 445–464. <https://doi.org/10.19233/ASHS.2024.30>.
- Constant, M., Alary, C., Weiss, L., Constant, A., Billon, G., 2023. Trapped microplastics within vertical redeposited sediment: experimental study simulating lake and channelled river systems during resuspension events. *Environ. Pollut.* 322, 121212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121212>.
- Cosoli, S., Ličer, M., Vodopivec, M., Malačič, V., 2013. Surface circulation in the Gulf of Trieste (northern Adriatic Sea) from radar, model, and ADCP comparisons. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 118, 6183–6200. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009261>.
- European Commission, 2017. COM(2017) 3 Final Report From The Commission To The European Parliament And The Council Assessing Member States' Monitoring Programmes under The Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Brussels.
- European Union, 2019. Directive 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the Reduction of the Impact of Certain Plastic Products on the Environment.
- Fleet, David, Vlachogianni, Thomas, Hanke, Georg, 2021. A Joint List of Litter Categories for Marine Macrolitter Monitoring (No. 978–92-76-21445-8). <https://doi.org/10.2760/127473>.
- Gago, J., Filgueiras, A., Pedrotti, M.L., Caetano, M., Frias, J., 2019. Standardised protocol for monitoring microplastics in seawater. Deliverable 4.1. <https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/1077> (Accessed 30 October 2025).
- Gajst, T., Bizjak, T., Palatinus, A., Liubartseva, S., Krzan, A., 2016. Sea surface microplastics in Slovenian part of the northern Adriatic. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 113, 392–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.10.031>.
- Galgani, F., Lusher, A.L., Strand, J., Haarr, M.L., Vinci, M., Molina Jack, E., Kagi, R., Aliani, S., Herzke, D., Nikiforov, V., Primpke, S., Schmidt, N., Fabres, J., De Witte, B., Solbakken, V.S., van Bavel, B., 2024. Revisiting the strategy for marine litter monitoring within the European marine strategy framework directive (MSFD). *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 255, 107254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107254>.
- Galgani, F., Ruiz-Orejón, L.F., Ronchi, F., Tallec, K., Fischer, E., Matiddi, M., Anastasopoulou, A., Andresmaa, E., Angiolillo, M., Bakker, M.P., Booth, A.M., Buhalko, N., Cadiou, B., Claro, F., Consoli, P., Darmon, G., Deudero, S., Fleet, D.M., Fortibuoni, T., Fossi, C.M., Gago, J., Gerigny, O., Giorgetti, A., Gonzalez, D.F., Guse, N., Haseler, M., Ioakeimidis, C., Kammann, U., Kühn, S., Lacroix, C., Lips, I., Loza, L.A., Jack, M.E.M., Noren, K., Papadoyannakis, M., Pragnell-Raasch, H., Rindorf, A., Ruiz, M., Setälä, O., Schulz, M., Schultze, M., Silvestri, C., Soederberg, L., Stoica, E., Storr-Paulsen, M., Strand, J., 2023. Guidance on the monitoring of marine litter in European seas: an update to improve the harmonised monitoring of marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. <https://doi.org/10.2760/59137>.
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J.R., Law, K.L., 2017. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci. Adv.* 3, e1700782. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1700782>.
- Graca, B., Szewc, K., Zakrzewska, D., Dolega, A., Szczerbowska-Boruchowska, M., 2017. Sources and fate of microplastics in marine and beach sediments of the southern Baltic Sea—a preliminary study. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24, 7650–7661. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-8419-5>.
- Grubar, V.B., 2010. Stanje okoliša slovenskog dijela Jadranskog mora. *Geoadria* 15, 49–80. <https://doi.org/10.15291/geoadria.544>.
- Hammer, Ø., Harper, D., Ryan, P., 2001. *PAST: paleontological statistics software package for education and data analysis*. *Paleoentol. Electron.* 4, 1–9.
- Hanke, G., Galgani, F., Werner, S., Oosterbaan, L., Nilsson, P., Fleet, D., Kinsey, S., Thompson, R., Palatinus, A., Van Franeker, J., Vlachogianni, T., Scoullas, M., Veiga, J., Matiddi, M., Alcaro, L., Maes, T., Korpinen, S., Budziak, A., Leslie, H., Gago, J., Liebezeit, G., 2013. Guidance on monitoring of marine litter in European seas: a guidance document within the common implementation strategy for the marine strategy framework directive. European Commission, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2788/99475>.
- Hardesty, B.D., Lawson, T., van der Velde, T., Lansdell, M., Wilcox, C., 2017. Estimating quantities and sources of marine debris at a continental scale. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 15, 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1447>.
- Haseler, M., Ben Abdallah, L., El Fels, L., El Hayany, B., Hassan, G., Escobar-Sánchez, G., Robbe, E., von Thenen, M., Loukili, A., Abd El-Raouf, M., Mhiri, F., El-Bary, A.A., Schernewski, G., Nassour, A., 2025. Assessment of beach litter pollution in Egypt, Tunisia, and Morocco: a study of macro and meso-litter on Mediterranean beaches. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 197, 123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-024-13517-x>.
- Haseler, M., Weder, C., Buschbeck, L., Wesnigk, S., Schernewski, G., 2019. Cost-effective monitoring of large micro- and meso-litter in tidal and flood accumulation zones at South-Western Baltic Sea beaches. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 149, 110544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.110544>.
- Hengstmann, E., Tamminga, M., vom Bruch, C., Fischer, E.K., 2018. Microplastic in beach sediments of the isle of Rügen (Baltic Sea) - implementing a novel glass elutriation column. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 126, 263–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.11.010>.
- Hernandez, I., Castro-Rosero, L.M., Espino, M., Alsina, J.M., 2025. Processes controlling the dispersion and beaching of floating marine debris in the Barcelona coastal region. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1534678>.
- Jaouani, R., Mouneyrac, C., Châtel, A., Amiard, F., Dellali, M., Beyrem, H., Michelet, A., Lagarde, F., 2022. Seasonal and spatial distribution of microplastics in sediments by FTIR imaging throughout a continuum lake - lagoon - beach from the Tunisian coast. *Sci. Total Environ.* 838, 156519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156519>.
- Jualang, S., Pransilpa, M., Pradit, S., Towatana, P., 2021. Type and distribution of microplastics in beach sediment along the coast of the eastern gulf of Thailand. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 9, 1405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9121405>.

- Jug, Metka, Kobetič, L., Britovšek, Jug, Manca, Vidmar, T., Lipušček, N., 2020. Občinski prostorski načrt Občine Ankaran. Okoljsko poročilo za izvedbo postopka CPVO za OPN Ankaran. https://www.obcina-ankaran.si/storage/doc/202010/opankaran_usklpredlogdopolnitev-drsv2oddaja.pdf (Accessed 29 November 2025).
- Khuyen, V.T.K., Le, D.V., Fischer, A.R., Dornack, C., 2021. Comparison of microplastic pollution in beach sediment and seawater at UNESCO can Gio mangrove biosphere reserve. *Global Chall.* 5, 2100044. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202100044>.
- Kovač Viršek, M., Bizjak, T., Robič, U., Kepec, M., Trdan, Š., Mihelič, P., 2024. Poročilo o delu Inštituta za vode Republike Slovenije za leto 2024 : 4 PRIPRAVA IN SODELOVANJE PRI RAZVOJU METODOLOGIJ ZA IZVAJANJE DIREKTIVE 2008/56/ES EVROPSKEGA PARLAMENTA IN SVETA Z DNE 17. JUNJA 2008 O DOLOČITVI OKVIRA ZA UKREPE SKUPNOSTI NA PODROČJU POLITIKE MORSKEGA OKOLJA, ZADNJIČ SPREMENJENE 17. MAJA 2017: 4.4 Nadgradnja metodologije za izvajanje monitoringa morskega okolja za primarni merili D10C1 in D10C2 z novimi podatki in nadaljevanje naloge iz leta 2023. In: Inštitut za vode Republike Slovenije. Ljubljana, Slovenia.
- Markič, A., Iveša, N., Budiša, A., Kovačić, I., Burič, P., Pustijanac, E., Buršič, M., Banai, B., Legin, D.P., Palatinus, A., Tutman, P., 2024. Fragmented marine plastics as the prevalent litter type on a small island beach in the Adriatic. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 203, 116467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116467>.
- MSFD, 2008, 2008. Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) - 2008/56 - EN - EUR-Lex.
- MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter, Hanke, G., Walvoort, D., Ruiz-Orejón, L.F., Van Loon, W.M.G.M., Giorgetti, A., Molina-Jack, M.E., Vinci, M., 2025. European Coastline Macro Litter Trends 2015–2021. <https://doi.org/10.2760/0752301>.
- Nayanathara Thathsarani Pilapitiya, P.G.C., Ratnayake, A.S., 2024. The world of plastic waste: a review. *Cleaner Mater.* 11, 100220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2024.100220>.
- NIB, MBP, 2025. OCEANOGRAPHIC BUOY VIDA, National Institute of Biology (NIB), Marine Biology Station Piran (MBP) [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.nib.si/mbp/en/oceanographic-data-and-measurements/buoy-2>. (Accessed 30 November 2025).
- Nielsen, M.B., Clausen, L.P.W., Cronin, R., Hansen, S.F., Oturai, N.G., Syberg, K., 2023. Unfolding the science behind policy initiatives targeting plastic pollution. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics* 3, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-022-00046-y>.
- Pakhomova, S., Zhdanov, I., van Bavel, B., 2020. Polymer type identification of marine plastic litter using a miniature near-infrared spectrometer (MicroNIR). *Appl. Sci.* 10, 8707. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10238707>.
- PlasticsEurope, 2023. *Plastics – the fast Facts 2023*.
- Primpke, S., Wirth, M., Lorenz, C., Gerdtz, G., 2018. Reference database design for the automated analysis of microplastic samples based on Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 410, 5131–5141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-018-1156-x>.
- Ramšak, A., Bizjak, T., Robič, U., Viršek, M.K., 2024. The need for innovations to secure the future of artisanal mussel farming in the coastal sea of the Gulf of Trieste (Slovenia). *Aquacult. Rep.* 36, 102166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2024.102166>.
- Republika Slovenija, 2022. Uredba o izvajanju Sklepa (EU) o merilih in metodoloških standardih na področju dobrega okoljskega stanja morskih voda ter specifikacijah in standardiziranih metodah za spremljanje ter presojo in razveljavitvi Sklepa 2010/477/EU. Uradni list RS, št. 156/2022 z dne 14. 12. 2022.
- Schröder, K., Kossel, E., Lenz, M., 2021. Microplastic abundance in beach sediments of the Kiel Fjord, Western Baltic Sea. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 28, 26515–26528. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-12220-x>.
- Schulz, M., Walvoort, D.J.J., Barry, J., Fleet, D.M., van Loon, W.M.G.M., 2019. Baseline and power analyses for the assessment of beach litter reductions in the European OSPAR region. *Environ. Pollut.* 248, 555–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.02.030>.
- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2025. URL <https://www.stat.si/statweb>. (Accessed 29 November 2025).
- Tsering, T., Sillanpää, M., Viitala, M., Reinikainen, S.P., 2022. Variation of microplastics in the shore sediment of high-altitude lakes of the Indian Himalaya using different pretreatment methods. *Sci. Total Environ.* 849, 157870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157870>.
- UNEP/MAP, 2021. Agenda Item 8: Cross-Cutting Issues - The Integration and Aggregation Rules for IMAP Ecological Objectives 5, 9 and 10 and Assessment Criteria for Contaminants, Nutrients and Marine Litter: Updated Baseline Values and Proposal for Threshold Values for IMAP Common Indicator 22. Meeting of the MED POL Focal Points - Videoconference, 26–27 May 2021. (No. WG.509/11). Athens.
- Van Loon, W., Hanke, G., Fleet, D., Werner, S., Barry, J., Strand, J., Eriksson, J., Galgani, F., Gräwe, D., Schulz, M., Vlachogianni, T., Press, M., Blidberg, E., Walvoort, D., 2020. A European Threshold Value and Assessment Method for Macro Litter on the Coastlines, vols. No. 978-92-76-21444-1. Luxembourg.
- Vlachogianni, T., Fortibuoni, T., Ronchi, F., Zerri, C., Mazzotti, C., Tutman, P., Varezić, D.B., Palatinus, A., Trdan, Š., Peterlin, M., Mandić, M., Markovic, O., Prvan, M., Kaberi, H., Prevenios, M., Kolutari, J., Kroqi, G., Fusco, M., Kalampokis, E., Scoullou, M., 2018. Marine litter on the beaches of the Adriatic and Ionian seas: an assessment of their abundance, composition and sources. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 131, 745–756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.05.006>.
- Vlachogianni, T., Scoullou, M., 2023. Assessing marine macrolitter on the coastline of the Asterousia biosphere reserve: insights from a community-based study. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 195, 115474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115474>.
- Windsor, F.M., Durance, I., Horton, A.A., Thompson, R.C., Tyler, C.R., Ormerod, S.J., 2019. A catchment-scale perspective of plastic pollution. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 1207–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14572>.
- Wright, S.L., Thompson, R.C., Galloway, T.S., 2013. The physical impacts of microplastics on marine organisms: a review. *Environ. Pollut.* 178, 483–492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.02.031>.
- Zou, H.-H., He, P.-J., Peng, W., Lan, D.-Y., Xian, H.-Y., Lü, F., Zhang, H., 2025. Rapid detection of colored and colorless macro- and micro-plastics in complex environment via near-infrared spectroscopy and machine learning. *J. Environ. Sci.* 147, 512–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jes.2023.12.004>.